

ASSESSMENT OF PRESCRIBING PATTERN AND RESISTANCE STATUS OF ANTIBIOTICS IN CRITICAL CARE UNIT OF TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: India is one of the countries with the highest rates of bacterial infections. The crude death rate from infectious diseases in India currently is 417 per 100,000 individuals. As a result, AMR is anticipated to have a greater impact in India. **AIM:** The current study was conducted to assess the prescribing pattern and resistance status of antibiotics in Critical Care Unit of tertiary care hospital, who admitted the GGH, Kadapa. **METHODS:** It was a prospective, observational, cohort-type study conducted in GGH, Kadapa, with a sample size of 104 ICU patients selected viewing the willingness and inclusive criteria. The Institutional Human Ethical Committee of the GGH, Kadapa approved the study. Appropriate statistical methods were employed for the data analysis. **RESULTS:** Among the 102 patients' males were high in number and the age group of 58-68 was the most commonly admitted group in ICU. Sputum was the most commonly analysed specimen and the isolated organism was *Klebsiella pneumonia* (16). Based on the susceptibility profile ampicillin showed resistance in overall ICU whereas ciprofloxacin showed resistance in antibiotics prescribed with multiple resistance. The clinical outcomes were also assessed at the time of admission and discharge by comparing their laboratory investigation are significance ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$). **CONCLUSION:** The study concludes that all the antibiotics were prescribed as per the standard treatment guidelines. Among the antibiotics prescribed in the intensive care unit, ciprofloxacin showed high resistance whereas Piperacillin + Tazobactam (commonly prescribed antibiotic) showed high sensitivity, irrespective of the system or organ affected and the isolated microorganism.

Keywords: Intensive care unit, Antibiotics resistance, sensitivity, prescribing pattern, microorganisms.

INTRODUCTION:

Antibiotics are the substances produced by the microorganisms, which selectively suppress the growth of or kill other microorganisms at very low concentrations. This definition excludes other natural subjects which also inhibit microorganisms but are produced by higher forms (antibodies).⁽¹⁾ Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) develops when bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites evolve over time and no longer respond to antibiotics, making disease conditions more difficult to treat and increasing the risk of disease spread, severe illness, and death. Antibiotics are becoming increasingly ineffective as drug-resistance spreads globally leading to more difficult to treat infections and death.⁽²⁾

India is one of the countries with the highest rates of bacterial infections. The crude death rate from infectious diseases in India currently is 417 per 100,000 individuals. As a result, AMR is anticipated to have a greater impact in India. AMR is a serious public health threat in India. The rapidly increasing proportion of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates in India appears to be indicative of AMR's rising tide. In 2008, around 29% of isolates were methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), but by 2014, this had increased to 47%.⁽³⁾ The aim of the study is to assess the prescribing pattern and resistance status of antibiotics in Critical Care Unit of tertiary care hospital.

Objectives of the study include:

- To categorise the patients based on demographics such as age, gender.
- To differentiate the patients treated with different antibiotics.
- To identify the most commonly isolated microorganisms in Intensive care unit.
- To assess the sensitivity of antibiotics.
- To assess the antibiotics resistance status in Critical care unit

- If any adverse drug reaction suspected will be reported.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Study design: It was a prospective, observational, cohort-type study, conducted in a Critical care unit at the Government General Hospital, Kadapa.

Study period: The present study was conducted for a period of six months from August 2023 to January 2024.

Inclusion criteria:

The study includes if the subject satisfies the following criteria:

- ✓ Patients who had undergone the treatment between the age group of above 18 years of both genders in the ICU department.
- ✓ Patients who were prescribed antibiotics of any dosage form
- ✓ Patients with or without co-morbidities.

Exclusion criteria:

The study excludes the following subjects:

- × Pregnancy and lactating women.
- × Patients / patient's representative who are not willing to participate in the study.
- × Patients who are referred to ICU from other departments (surgery, cardiac disorders)

Source of data:

Data was collected from patient case sheets and culture sensitivity reports (C/S) from the microbiology lab for those who were admitted to the Critical Care Unit.

Study area:

Government General Hospital, Kadapa.

Appropriate statistical methods were employed for the data analysis they are:

- Microsoft Excel spreadsheets were used to record all of the recruited subjects' data.
- Descriptive statistics was used for the estimation of results and the Single paired t-test for the comparison of clinical outcomes.

RESULTS

Distribution of subjects based on Age group and Gender

A total of 104 subjects constituted the study sample that we employed for this research..

Out of all the subjects, male subjects were 65 (63.72%) and female subjects were 37 (36.27%). The preponderance of subjects was in the age group of 58-68 i.e.,24 (23.52%). Of which, male and female participants constitute 14 (13.72%) and 10 (9.80%) which was represented in figure1 respectively.

Figure 1. Categorization of the subjects based on Age group and Gender

The average age of subjects in our study was found to be 56.2 ± 16.03 .

The average length of stay of subjects was found to be 7.6 ± 1.3 days.

Categorization of most commonly used and effective Antibiotics in Intensive Care Unit

In this study, a total of 218 antibiotics were prescribed across 102 subjects. The distribution of prescribed antibiotics showed that Penicillin's + Beta-lactamase inhibitors were the most common (61), followed by Cephalosporins (45), Macrolides (31), Cephalosporins + Beta-lactamase inhibitors (20), Carbapenems, Tetracyclines, and Nitroimidazoles (14), Fluoroquinolones (9), Glycopeptides (5), Others (4), and Aminoglycosides (1).

On average **2 antibiotics** were prescribed to the subjects in Intensive Care Unit.

Figure 2. Illustration of the Most commonly used antibiotics in the Intensive Care Unit Distribution based on Type of antibiotic therapy

In the study involving 102 subjects, the majority of subjects (62) were prescribed multiple therapy, while the least number of subjects, (7) received monotherapy.

Distribution of subjects based on Route of Administration

In a cohort of 102 subjects, the majority of subjects 55 (53.9%), received medications through the parental route of administration. The remaining 47 (46.07%) subjects, were administered drugs through a combination of oral and parental routes.

Distribution based on the type of Specimen analyzed

The microbiological culture and sensitivity in different body specimens were analyzed. The most common specimen sent for microbiology lab was sputum 68 (66.6%).

Distribution of subjects based on organism isolated

In our study, unidentical microorganisms were isolated from different specimens involving all the subjects, among them 78(76.47%) tested positive for bacterial growth, while the remaining 24(23.52%) tested negative.

Among the positively tested subjects, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (16) was the most isolated organism in 68 subjects of lower respiratory tract infection, *Escherichia coli* (9) was the most isolated organism in 24 subjects of urinary tract infection, *staphylococcus aureus* (2) was the most isolated organism in 3 subjects of skin and soft tissue infections, *staphylococcus aureus* (1) and *Escherichia coli* (1) were the most isolated organisms in 2 subjects of intra-abdominal infections, *staphylococcus aureus*(2) was the most isolated organism in sepsis among 4 subjects and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (1) was the most isolated organism in the central nervous system among 1 subject which was shown in Table 1.

Distribution based on Susceptibility Profile

In the susceptibility profile of ICU patients, ampicillin showed higher resistance, while Piperacillin+ Tazobactam had higher sensitivity which was shown in Table 2.

In the ICU, ciprofloxacin exhibited higher resistance among prescribed antibiotics, while Piperacillin+ Tazobactam showed higher sensitivity which was shown in Table 3.

DISCUSSION

The **demographic data** in our study indicated that the majority of subjects were males aged between (58 – 68), with an average age of 56.2, which was related to study carried out by **Rachel Thomas et al. (2019)**.⁽⁴⁾

The average length of stay of subjects in our study was 7.6 ± 1.3 days which was similar to the result findings of **Eldalo A. et al. (2019)**.⁽⁵⁾

In our study, we observed that Penicillin + Beta-lactamase inhibitors were the most frequently prescribed antibiotics, with respiratory tract infections being the most commonly affected system, which was similar to the study conducted by **Jaime Elizabeth et al. (2022)**.⁽⁶⁾

The average number of antibiotics prescribed to the subjects in our study was 2, which was similar to the study conducted by **Pavithra et al. (2020)**.⁽⁷⁾

In our study, gram-negative organisms were most commonly isolated, which was similar to the study conducted by **Savanur S.S et al. (2017)**.⁽⁸⁾

In our study, Klebsiella pneumoniae was the most commonly isolated microorganism. Notably, we observed a high resistance to ampicillin, which was similar to the findings reported in the study conducted by **Leake Genremeskel et al. (2023)**.⁽⁹⁾

Piperacillin + Tazobactam shown high sensitivity in our study, which is consistent with the findings of **Gilani et al. (2016)**.⁽¹⁰⁾

Among the antibiotics prescribed to the subjects in the intensive care unit of our study ciprofloxacin showed higher resistance which was similar to the study of **Kotevska et al. (2020)**.⁽¹¹⁾

In our study, we observed that **initial therapy** demonstrated effectiveness for the majority of patients, with only a few requiring alternative antimicrobial agents based on culture and sensitivity reports. This study aligned with the findings reported in the study conducted by **Rajkhirasaria et al. (2019)**.⁽¹²⁾

In our study, we observed that bactericidal antibiotics were most commonly prescribed to the subjects in the intensive care unit.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results, our study concluded that all the antibiotics were prescribed as per the standard treatment guidelines. Penicillin + beta-lactamase inhibitors were the most commonly administered antibiotics (bactericidal) in that, Piperacillin+Tazobactam was most

commonly prescribed, irrespective of the system or organ affected and the isolated microorganism.

Based on the susceptibility profile of antibiotics, ampicillin had high resistance whereas Piperacillin+Tazobactam showed high sensitivity. Among the antibiotics prescribed in the intensive care unit, ciprofloxacin showed high resistance whereas Piperacillin+Tazobactam showed high sensitivity.

The Infection Control Committee and standard guidelines for the administration of antibiotics were closely followed, which led to successful outcomes in ICU patients. All physicians and patients play a significant role in preventing antibiotic resistance, and the key to antimicrobial success is recognizing when to start and discontinue. Antibiotic resistance is a major concern, which can be addressed by reserving antibiotics for future use through their judicious usage.

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Tables

System affected & Diagnosis (N)	Organism isolated	Gram Stain	Number of Subjects N (%)
Respiratory tract infections	CNBG	Nil	17 (16.6%)

(68) Pneumonia (37) COPD (31)	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	-ve	16 (15.6%)
	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	+ve	14 (13.7%)
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-ve	10 (9.8%)
	<i>co.neg. staphylococcus aureus</i>	+ve	5 (4.9%)
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-ve	5 (4.9%)
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+ve	1 (0.9%)
Urinary tract infections (24) UTI (21) Pyelonephritis (3)	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-ve	9 (8.8%)
	<i>co.neg. staphylococcus aureus</i>	+ve	8 (7.8%)
	CNBG	Nil	5 (4.9%)
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	-ve	2 (1.9%)
Skin and Soft tissue infections (3) Cellulitis (3)	<i>staphylococcus aureus</i>	+ve	2 (1.9%)
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-ve	1 (0.9%)
Intra-abdominal infections (2) Liver abscess (2)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	+ve	1 (0.9%)
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-ve	1 (0.9%)
Circulatory (4) Sepsis (4)	CNBG	Nil	2 (1.9%)
	<i>staphylococcus aureus</i>	+ve	2 (1.9%)
CNS infection (1) Meningitis (1)	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	-ve	1 (0.9%)

Table1. Categorization of the subjects based on isolated microorganisms

Antimicrobial agent	Number of subjects (78)	
	Resistance(N)	Sensitive(N)
Penicillin-G	5	0
Piperacillin + Tazobactam	3	42
Amoxicillin + Potassium Clavulanate	2	2
Cefoperazone + Sulbactam	1	0
Ceftriaxone	0	1
Cefotaxime	2	1
Ampicillin	48	4
Trimethoprim + Sulfamethoxazole	18	14
Gentamycin	12	40
Ciprofloxacin	21	32
Metronidazole	2	0
Amikacin	2	0
Vancomycin	1	15
Meropenem	6	6
Others	30	28

Table 2. Categorization based on the Susceptibility Profile in ICU

Drug Name	No. of subjects prescribed N (%)	No. of subjects with resistance N (%)	No. of subjects with sensitivity N (%)
Ciprofloxacin	7 (10.6%)	3 (60%)	3 (10.7%)

Clindamycin	2 (3%)	0 (0%)	2 (7.1%)
Piperacillin + tazobactam	41 (62.1%)	1 (20%)	22 (78.5%)
Cefotaxime	2 (3%)	1 (20%)	0 (0%)
Meropenem	14 (21.2%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.5%)
Total	66 (100%)	5 (100%)	28 (100%)

Table 3. Percentage distribution of Susceptibility Profile of subjects prescribed with antibiotics in ICU